

Gut Microbiota is A Crucial Bridge Mediating the Pharmacological Effect of Labiatae Traditional Chinese Medicine

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Abstract: Labiatae, a family of the dicotyledonous plants, has attracted extensive interest because of its wide application in foods, drugs and cosmetics. According to the National Census of Chinese Medicine Resources, Labiatae contains about dozens of medicinal plants with multiple pharmacological effects. As part of symbiosis with the host, gut microbiota is closely associated with host health, nutrition, and adaptability. Currently, several studies have revealed the molecular mechanism of Labiatae but only small part of them show the potential effect of the gut microbiota. In addition, most studies just concentrate on the regulation effect of traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) on gut microbiota. This unilateral study ignores the metabolic transformation role of gut microbiome on herb medicines, resulting in the lack of understanding of drug efficacy and pharmacological mechanism. This review, therefore, comprehensively and systematically summarized the active compounds and pharmacological effects of Labiatae, including *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge, *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, and *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt, and revealed the interaction between those TCMs with gut microbiota, thus promoting a further understanding of the efficacy and pharmacological mechanism of TCM. In the future study, Labiatae can be used as a prebiotic to modulate the structure and composition of gut microbiome to improve the human health status.

Keywords: Traditional Chinese medicine (TCM); Labiatae plants; Gut microbiota; Pharmacological effects; Probiotics.

Introduction

Labiatae is a large family of Dicotyledons, with about 99 genera and more than 808 species in China. Labiatae plants are rich in volatile oils and possess important medicinal value, for example, the essential oil from *Elsholtzia ciliata* (Thunb.) Hyland. can alleviate the symptom of class 1B arrhythmia in rabbit heart model and have potential effects for ventricular tachycardia^[1]. Similarly, as in vitro study shown, the nanocapsules made from peppermint oil can promote fibroblast proliferation and have promise in wound healing^[2]. Except for volatile oils, other components from Labiatae plants also participated in maintaining human healthy. Previous study displayed that *Leonurus artemisia* ethanol extract upregulated peroxisome proliferators-activated receptor- α (PPAR- α) and carnitine palmitoyltransferase-1 (CPT1) mRNA expression through the 5'-adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK)/acetyl-coenzyme A carboxylase (ACC) pathway, thus reduced lipid accumulation in HepG2 cells, implying that *Leonurus artemisia* was a potential nature medicine to treat non-alcoholic fatty liver^[3]. In addition, phenolic components in

Mentha haplocalyx Briq. exert potent effects in the inhibition of proinflammatory factors and cytokine production by inhibiting nuclear factor kappa-B (NF- κ B) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) in RAW264.7 cells, which is beneficial to inflammatory diseases^[4]. Although Labiatae plants possess several pharmacological activities, the involving mechanisms are poorly elucidated to a certain extent due to the complex of human metabolism.

Gut microbiota, the resident microorganisms in the human body, usually interacts with body's cells and systems and is shaped by host health status^[5]. Currently, researchers have bent their efforts to exploring relationship between gut microbiota and the efficacy of Labiatae TCM. Their results showed that gut microbiota mediated the pharmacological effect of TCM. The study on *Melissa officinalis* L. showed that its extracts enhanced the diversity of gut microbiota, increased the abundance of Porphyromonadaceae family, and activated microbial pathways associated with fatty acid metabolism while inhibiting sphingolipid metabolism in ob/ob mice^[6]. Furthermore, new monofloral honey in *Prunella vulgaris* L. can decrease the Bacteroides / Firmicutes ratio in rats with acute colitis, and restore the decreasing of *Lactobacillus spp.*, reduce the increasing of *Bacteroides spp.*^[7]. Above studies proved that the gut microbiota plays a crucial role in the pharmacological effect of Labiatae. However, the current study just focused on the regulation effect of Labiatae TCM on gut microbiota, few studies reveal the interaction effect between gut microbiota and TCM.

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This review comprehensively and systematically reviewed the active ingredients and pharmacological effects of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge, and *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt. Simultaneously, we tried to find the interaction effect between gut microbiota and Labiatae TCM, thus promoting a further understanding of the efficacy of TCM. Moreover, the review proposed that some TCM can be developed into prebiotics to accelerate the colonization of special probiotics, which are in favor of host body health.

1. Active ingredients and pharmacological effects of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi

The main active component of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi is flavonoids, including baicalin, baicalein, wogonoside and wogonin (Fig. 1). Modern studies show that *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi is effective in neuroprotection^[8], anti-inflammatory^[9], antioxidant^[10], anti-tumor^[11], and liver protection^[12]. And those pharmacological effects are closely related to the content of flavonoid components (Fig. 2).

1.1. Antitumor effect of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi

As the major component of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, baicalin could inhibit leukemia cell lines with rearranged *MLL* and *PBX1* genes, which mainly relied on inhibiting cell proliferation, increasing the levels of cytochrome C and activating caspase3/7 to induce cell death^[13]. Additionally, baicalin treatment for forty-eight hours significantly inhibited cell proliferation rate of CA46-Burkitt lymphoma cells, and it was probably due to the inhibition of the PI3K/Akt signaling pathway^[14]. Baicalein is another ex-

tract of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, it down-regulates the expression of inhibitory apoptotic protein family members (cIAP-1 and cIAP-2), activates caspase-9/3 and promotes the degradation of poly (ADP-ribose)-polymerase in human bladder cancer 5637 cells^[15]. In addition to the above pathways, whether other pathways are involved in the antitumor effect of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi needs to be further explored.

1.2. Anti-microbial and anti-viral effects of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi

The study on anti-microbial and anti-viral effects of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi showed that 80% ethanol extracts of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi contained the highest levels of baicalin, wogonoside, baicalein, wogonin, and chrysin, which inhibited the growth of harmful bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*^[16]. In addition, baicalein could resist four common human pathogenic fungi (*Trichophyton rubrum*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans*). Wogonin displayed antifungal activity against *T. rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes* and *A. fumigatus*^[17]. On the other aspect, the extracts of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi also showed anti-viral effect on coliphage MS2 (MS2), a bacterial virus infecting *E. coli*^[16]. Baicalin, one of component of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, could restrain Marek's disease virus by inhibiting viral mRNA and protein levels, thus directly affected the virus infectivity in CEF cells^[18]. Moreover, Baicalin interfered with the interaction of HIV-1 with chemokine coreceptors and block HIV-1 entering to target cells^[19]. Therefore, the extracts of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi are promising nature medicines to against bacteria and viruses.

Fig. 1. Structure of main active components of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi.

Fig. 2. The pharmacological effects of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi.

1.3. Anti-inflammatory effect of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi

Previous study showed that baicalin inhibited the secretion of interleukin 6 (IL-6), IL-8 and tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α) in osteoarthritis, and protected CHON-001 cells from IL-1 β -induced inflammatory injury probably through down-regulating the expression of miR-126 and thus inactivating nuclear factor-kappaB (NF- κ B) signaling pathway^[20,21]. The baicalin also effectively reduces amount of activated microglia and concentration of proinflammatory cytokines in APP/PS1 mice and lipopolysaccharide (LPS) /A β -stimulated BV2 microglia cells, which mainly via downregulating the expression of NLRP3 inflammasomes and the TLR4/NF- κ B signaling pathway^[22]. Moreover, baicalin can significantly suppress the methionine and choline-deficient diet-induced hepatic inflammatory response in mice by reducing serum TNF- α , IL-1 β and monocyte chemoattractant protein (MCP-1) production, influx of macrophage, as well as inhibiting NF- κ B activation^[23]. The anti-inflammatory effect of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi is indubitable, but the deeper mechanisms are elucidated insufficiently due to the complex of inflammation response. New theories and research ideas need to be put forward to reveal the more precise mechanisms.

1.4. Antioxidant effect of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi

The *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi also have the potential of antioxidants. It is well known that the reactive oxygen species (ROS) can lead to the damage of dopaminergic neurons, while baicalin reverses this negative effect. Simultaneously, baicalin reduced the expression of C/EBP β and α -synuclein expression in pLVX-Tet3G- α -synuclein SH-SY5Y cells^[24]. Another component of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, baicalein, plays a neuroprotective role by preventing 6-hydroxydopamine-induced oxidative damage in PC12 cells by activating the Keap1/Nrf2/HO-1 pathway^[25]. Furthermore, baicalein treatment also significantly reversed the increasing of IL-6, IL-1 β and TNF- α in serum and liver, decreased hepatic malondialdehyde (MDA) concentration and depletion of superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione (GSH), catalase (CAT) in mice with a dose-dependent manner^[26]. Stud-

ies widely revealed that oxidative stress is the main cause of aging and some disease. So *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi can regulate human health through inhibiting oxidative stress.

2. Active ingredients and pharmacological effects of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

There are two main types of active ingredients in *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge, including lipid-soluble components, such as tanshinone I, tanshinone IIA, tanshinone IIB, dihydrotanshinone I, cryptotanshinone, and so on; and water-soluble components, such as danshensu (3-(3, 4-dihydroxyphenyl) lactic acid), salvianolic acid A, salvianolic acid B, rosmarinic acid, caffeic acid, protocatechuic acid, caffeic acid, and so on^[27] (Fig. 3). The enriched chemical components result in a variety of pharmacological effects of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge, which involving in treatment of cardiovascular disease^[12], tumor^[28], ulcerative disease^[29], and hepatocirrhosis^[30] (Fig. 4).

2.1. Anti-inflammatory effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

Salvianolic acid B in *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge is able to decrease the levels of nitric oxide (NO), TNF- α , IL-1 β and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in LPS-induced primary microglia of rats, thereby protect rats from microglial-mediated neuroinflammation^[31]. Similarly, cryptotanshinone could protect neurons from inflammatory injury, which relied on activating of Nrf2/HO-1 pathway, then down-regulated proinflammatory factors in BV-2 microglial cells^[32]. Magnesium lithospermate B, an active compound of *Salvia miltiorrhiza*, has beneficial effects on inflammatory response of arteriosclerosis through decreasing IL-2, IL-4, TNF- α and interferon γ (IFN- γ) levels in activated T cells, and inhibiting the DNA-binding activity of the activated protein-1 (AP-1), NF- κ B and octamer-binding transcription factor 1 (OCT1) in human peripheral T lymphocytes^[33]. Salvianolic acid A could also regulate NF- κ B inflammatory pathways via inhibiting I κ B α phosphorylation and degradation in vitro^[34]. We can see different

Fig. 3. Structure of main active components of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge.

Fig. 4. The pharmacological effects of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge.

components of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge are all exerted anti-inflammatory effect. However, the difference or similarities of these anti-inflammatories are less explained, which need to be further explored in the future study.

2.2. Anti-oxidative stress effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

Emerging evidence exhibited that excessive glucose promotes reactive oxygen species (ROS) production and leads to the damage of vascular^[35]. Salvianolic acid A could block ROS production in

vascular endothelial cells with in a concentration dependent manner, which subsequently inhibited proliferation of human umbilical vein endothelial cell induced by angiotensin^[36]. Another in vivo study also revealed that both salvianolic acid A and salvianolic acid B inhibited the expression of alpha-smooth muscle actin(α -SMA) and NADPH oxidase subunits gp91(phox) and p47(phox) in membrane fractions stimulated by platelet-derived growth factor, decreased ROS production and suppressed hepatic fibrotic caused by oxidative stress^[37]. In addition, salvia miltiorrhiza injection exerted antioxidative effects on high glucose treated vascular smooth muscle cells through inhibiting expression of Krüppel-like factor 10 (KLF10), an inducible early gene for transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β), and thus upregulating heme oxygenase (HO-1)^[38]. However, whether the main component which exerted antioxidative effects is salvianolic acid or other components has not been revealed yet.

2.3. Antitumor effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

Salvia miltiorrhiza Bunge is proved to exert antitumor in several studies. For example, tanshinone IIA was an active component for the treatment of liver cancer, and this effect was achieved by inhibiting tumor cell growth and migration, as well as induce liver cancer cell apoptosis in vitro and in vivo^[28]. The tanshinone analog 2-((Glycine methyl ester) methyl)-naphtho restrained the migration and invasion of prostate cancer cells through alteration of vascular endothelial growth factor 1/matrix metalloproteinase 9 (VEGF1/MMP-9) signaling pathway in vivo, thus became a potential component in the treatment of prostate cancer^[39]. The combination of Cefprozil and Tanshinone makes patients with mastitis got better outcomes than Cefprozil treated alone^[40], implying that Tanshinone may be a potential compound in preventing the occurrence of breast cancer.

2.4. Anti-hepatic fibrosis effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

It has been reported that *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge partially antagonized ASGM-1-induced natural killing (NK) cell loss, enhances cell activity and suppresses hepatic stellate cell (HSC) activation in vitro, and attenuates hepatic fibrosis by enhancing NK cell activity in vivo^[30]. Active components in *Salvia miltiorrhiza* also possess anti-fibrotic effects, for example, salvianolic acid B can mitigate liver fibrosis by regulating TGF- β /Smad and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways^[41]. PF2401-SF in *Salvia miltiorrhiza* also reduced the activation of hepatic astrocytes and down-regulated the protein and mRNA expression of collagen 1(α) and tissue inhibitor of metalloproteinase (TIMP)1, which plays an anti-fibrotic role in the thioacetamide-induced rats model^[42].

2.5. Protection effect on cardiovascular system of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

The protection for the cardiovascular system is systemic effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge. Existing studies have shown that *Salvia miltiorrhiza* injection can significantly alleviate myocardial fibrosis, myocardial hypertrophy, hemodynamic deterioration, and systolic and diastolic dysfunction in patients with heart fail-

ure^[43]. Danqi pill, consisted of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge and *Panax notoginseng*, alleviated cardiac function and myocardial ischemia in rats with coronary heart diseases via upregulating the expression of p-AMPK and p-TSC2, while downregulating the expression of p-mTOR in myocardial tissue^[44]. Some component of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge also plays an essential role in the cardiovascular system. For example, tanshinone IIA significantly inhibited rats smooth muscle cell proliferation and migration, thereby mediating pathological vascular remodeling through changing smooth muscle cell phenotype conversion in KLF4-mediated manner^[12]. Another component, dihydrotanshinone I, can also serve as a novel cardioprotective agent to ameliorate cardiotoxicity induced by doxorubicin in C57BL/6 mice via mTOR-TFEB-NF- κ B signaling pathway^[45,46]. However, the difference between the efficacy of monomer components and mixed components remains to be further explored.

3. Active ingredients and pharmacological effects of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

The main officinal part of *Perilla* is its leaves, which contains volatile oil (perilla oil), flavonoids (luteolin, apigenin), phenolic acid (rosmarinci acid), polysaccharide and other components^[47] (Fig. 5), among which, perilla oil, rosmarinci acid are relatively much studied. The main pharmacological effects of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt are antioxidation, anti-inflammation, anti-anaphylaxis, et al (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5. Structure of main active components of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt.

3.1. Antioxidation effect of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

Oral administration of *Perilla* can prolong the oxidation lag of LDL in human body, and reduce lipid peroxide formation and electrophoretic mobility of LDL^[48]. This result showed that *Perilla* has high antioxidant activity. The highest content of rosmarinci acid usually yield from perilla leaves ethanol extract and exerts the strongest antioxidant effect^[49]. It significantly inhibited MMP-1 and MMP-3 expression, inactivated UV-induced mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) signaling, along with de-

Fig. 6. The pharmacological effects of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt.

ing the secretion of UV-induced ROS in human dermal fibroblasts and Skh-1 mice^[49,50]. Another study also showed that the highest rosmarinci acid content in the ethyl acetate fraction of perilla seed significantly down-regulated RANKL-induced NF-κB, AP-1 activation, and inhibited the expression of activated T cell nuclear factor 1 (NFATc1) and ROS generation in RANKL-induced RAW 264.7 cells^[51]. Rosmarinci acid may be a major component of *Perilla* that exerted the potent antioxidant effect.

3.2. Anti-inflammatory effect of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

Inflammation reaction is always accompanied by the secretion of inflammatory cytokine. *Perilla frutescens* leaf extract could inhibit pro-inflammatory cytokine secretion, such as TNF-α, IL-1β, IL-6 and IL-17A, and induce the production of anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10, thereby possessed the potential preventive and restorative effects on dextran sulfate sodium (DSS) induced-colitis^[52]. The rosmarinci acid methyl ester, one component of mutant cultivar of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt also inhibited the expression of LPS-induced proinflammatory cytokines in RAW 264.7 Cells^[53]. Therefore, *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt is a potential herbal medicine to prevent inflammation related disease.

3.3. Neuro-protection effect of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

The study on *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt revealed that the hexane extraction of perilla leaves was able to effectively reduce beta-amyloid (Aβ) aggregation and promote the decomposition of

Aβeta precursor, thus protecting PC12 cells from Aβeta aggregation-induced toxicity. Meanwhile, the extract significantly reduced nitric oxide (NO) production in LPS-stimulated BV2 microglia, thereby exerted a neuroprotective role and possessed the potential to prevent and treat alzheimer's disease^[54]. Luteolin from mature perilla seeds significantly inhibited ROS production, and prevented reduced mitochondrial and catalase activity in vitro, thus protecting nervous system by maintaining a balance of pro-oxidant and anti-oxidant state^[55]. All of these results suggest that *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt have the potential to ameliorate the symptoms of parkinson, alzheimer's disease, and other neuro-related diseases.

3.4. Anti-anaphylaxis effect of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

Anaphylaxis is a compensatory immune response of the human body to allergens. A in vivo and in vitro study showed that perilla extracts significantly prevented DNP-IgE-induced TNF-α production and inhibited mast cell-mediated immediate-type hypersensitivity reaction^[56]. *Perilla* extracts also have a strong anti-atopic dermatitis activity, which can significantly reduce the immune response and result in reduced levels of eosinophils in adjacent skin tissues^[57]. In addition, roseoside (RosS), vicenin-2 (Vic-2) and rosmarinci acid (RosA) from perilla leaves extract significantly inhibited the expression and phosphorylation of allergic asthma-related proteins in allergic mice and RBL-2H3 cells, which may benefit to allergic airway inflammation^[58]. Although studies proved that *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt can prevent anaphylaxis, the specificity has not been explained. Future studies

should reveal which type of allergic reaction is responding to *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt effectively.

3.5. Improving metabolism effect of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

The metabolic disease gradually attracted much attention due to their widely harmful consequences. Finding some herbal foods or medicines is an effective approach to maintain human metabolism balance. A study about the effect of perilla oil on metabolic disorders caused by high fat diet revealed that perilla oil regulated intestinal inflammation and permeability, modulating intestinal lipid metabolism and cholesterol metabolism, indicating that perilla oil has the potential effect on metabolism disorder. Similarly, supplement with perilla oil promoted the recovery of hypertriglyceridemia in diabetic KKAY mice and balanced their gut dysbiosis^[46]. Luteolin, rosmarinci acid, rutin, and catechin in perilla leaves can significantly reduce serum glucose levels in streptozocin-induced diabetic rats, modulate total serum levels of cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (HDL-C), and high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol (LDL-C), and alleviate histopathology in liver and intestinal tissue^[59]. So, the *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt can be developed into a dietary supplement to regulate human health.

4. Interaction between gut microbiota and Labiatae plants

Gut microbiota, acting as a bridge that links the host and external environment, considerably contribute to the efficacy and mechanism of TCM. Several existing studies confirmed that gut microbiota would interact with TCM to maintain human health. On the one hand, TCM alters the structure and composition of gut microbiota to regulate the host health; on the other hand, gut microbiota can metabolite drugs or foods, thus affecting the efficacy of TCM^[60,61]. Therefore, exploring the interaction of gut microbiota with TCMs, such as *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge and *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt, can promote the understanding of pharmacological effects and mechanisms of Labiatae (Fig. 7).

4.1. Interaction between gut microbiota and *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi

The interaction between gut microbiota and *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi is mainly manifested in two aspects. Firstly, the gut microbiota can metabolize the component of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi to its active form and then exert pharmacological effect. For example, the β -glucuronidase, produced by gut microbiota (e.g., *Escherichia coli*), can metabolize baicalin to baicalein, which blocks the S phase cell cycle and promotes apoptotic in HCT-116 cells^[62]. The baicalein can also be reconverted into baicalin and 6-O-glucuronide through UDP-glucuronate syltransferases in the small intestine or liver^[63]. Therefore, the gut microbiota is closely associated with the high bioavailability of medicines in vivo.

Next, *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi will alter the structure and composition of host gut microbiota to modulate the balance of human metabolism. It is reported that orally treatment spontan-

Fig. 7. The interaction between gut microbiota and Labiatae.

eous hypertensive rats with baicalin enriched short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs)-producing bacteria, such as *Streptococcus*, *Akkermansia*, *Allobaculum*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Lachnospiraceae_NK4B4*, *Prevotella-9* and *Roseburia*, and promoted the production of SCFAs, which maintaining intestinal integrity and reducing hypertension-related intestinal barrier damage^[64]. Baicalein treatment decreasing the level of *Escherichia Shigella*, *Bacteroides*, *Parabacteroides*, *Lactococcus*, *Enterococcus* and *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_1*, while increasing the abundance of Muribaculaceae in chemotherapy-induced intestinal mucositis mice. The correlation analysis showed that serum IL-6 and TNF- α were significantly associated with the abundance of *Clostridium_sensu_stricto_1*, *Enterococcus*, *Bacteroides* and *Lactococcus*^[65]. These means that baicalein changed the concentration of inflammatory factors through modulating gut microbiota, thus resisting inflammatory reaction. Moreover, SP2-1, a polysaccharide isolated from *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, can significantly increase the number of Firmicutes, *Bifidobacterium*, *Lactobacillus* and *Rosiella*, and inhibit the growth of Proteobacteria, *Bacteroides* and *Staphylococcus*, resulting in the enhanced levels of acetate, propionate and butyrate in DSS-induced ulcerative colitis mice^[66]. Furthermore, baicalin also could promote the efficacy of other drugs. For example, the combination of *Scutellaria baicalensis* decoction and metformin could increase the level of *Bacteroides* while decrease the level of Firmicutes, indicating this combination alleviated the diet-induced metabolic dysregulation in mice via the gut-liver-brain axis^[67].

4.2. Interaction between gut microbiota and *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge

Several studies have shown that *Salvia miltiorrhiza* and its active components can ameliorate the status and symptoms of disease by restoring the disorder of gut microbiota. For example, the ethanol extract of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* can regulate the levels of *Shuttleworthia*, *Peptostreptococcaceae* and *Pseudomonas* in chronic

renal failure rats. In contrast, water extract affects the genus of Peptococcus, peptostreptococcaceae and Ruminococcus^[68]. Therefore, *Salvia miltiorrhiza* can alleviate chronic renal failure by regulating the gut microbiota.

Salvianolic acid can also exert its efficacy by modulating the gut microbiota. It was shown that salvianolic acid combined triterpenoids from yeyachun could alleviate carbon tetrachloride-induced liver fibrosis in mice via regulating gut microbiota, especially regulated the proportion of Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes as well as metabolites of the gut microbiota^[69]. The intervention with total phenolic acid from stem and radix of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* can restore the gut microbiota disorder in the type 2 diabetic nephropathy model, which increases SCFAs-producing bacteria mainly *Lachnospiraceae*, *Rikenellaceae*, *Lachnospiraceae_UCG-001* and *Eubacterium nodatum* to enhance the content of SCFAs in the intestinal^[70]. Furthermore, salvianolic acid A can regulate the imbalance of gut microbiota in colitis rats by reversing the increased Bacteroidetes and decreased Firmicutes, and increasing the abundance of Verrucomicrobia phylum. Meanwhile, the genera of *Akkermansia*, *Lactobacillus*, *Lachnospiraceae*, *Bacillus* spp. and *Blautia* spp. were enriched, while *Bacteroides*, *Roseburia* and *Ruminiclostridium* spp. were lowered after salvianolic acid A treatment^[71].

The polysaccharide is another main component of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* and has several pharmacological effects. SMWP-U&E, one of the polysaccharides in residue of *Salvia miltiorrhiza*, enhanced the indices of diversity of gut microbial communities in both large intestine and small intestine of weaned piglets. The abundance of *Lactobacillus* in the jejunum was increased, while the abundance of *Escherichia coli* in jejunum, ileum, cecum, and colon were decreased^[72]. These regulation effects were closely related to its antioxidant activity. Additionally, the mixture of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* polysaccharide, *Bifidobacterium bifidum* V and *Lactobacillus plantarum* X can decrease the level of Cyanobacteria phylum, *Oscillospira* and *Alistipes* genus, while increasing the level of *Bacteroides*, *Lactobacillus* and *Parabacteroides* genus in high-fat-diet (HFD)-fed mice. Therefore, it can be used as a therapeutic drug to improve non-alcoholic fatty liver disease^[73].

In addition to the above components, cryptotanshinone can decrease Muribaculaceae but increase *Lactobacillus*, *Alistipes* and *Oscillospira* to regulate lipid metabolism and alleviate 5FU/CPT-11-induced colitis in colitis-associated carcinogenesis mice^[74]. Dihydrodanshinone I can reverse the disturbance of the gut microbiota to near normal levels in mice, which manifests in increasing the abundance of *Akkermansia*, Ruminococcaceae, *Butyrivibrio*, Muribaculaceae, Lachnospiraceae_UCG_006 and Clostridiales_vadinBB60. *Akkermansia* can produce acetate and propionic acid, which is associated with healthy mucosal status^[75]. It is seen that dihydrodanshinone I have an effect on chemotherapy-induced intestinal mucositis by modulating the gut microbiota composition and decreasing the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines.

There is no doubt that the interaction relationship between *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge and gut microbiota. However, the above research showing that most studies are only devoted to observe the regulatory effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* or its active components on the gut microbiota, the metabolism of the components of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* by gut microbiota are ignored. Future study should be more comprehensive to promote the in-depth understanding of the pharmacological effect and mechanism of

Salvia miltiorrhiza.

4.3. Interaction between gut microbiota and *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt

It was shown that perilla extract could enhance the abundance of Actinobacteria, Firmicutes and Spirochaetes. The supplementation with Perilla leaves significantly increased the levels of *Acetivibrio*, *Marvinbryantia*, *Eubacterium coprostanoligenes*, *Selenomonas_1*, *Ruminococcus gauvreauii*, *Pseudoscardovia*, *Sharpea* and *Muribaculaceae*, while decreased the abundance of *Treponema_2* in cows^[76]. Therefore, the *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt can regulate the composition of gut microbiota to maintain the balance of host body.

Perilla oil, the main active component of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt, could reduce the levels of *Prevotella* and *Escherichia* but increased the abundance of Spirochaetes in HFD-induced alcoholic fatty liver disease, thereby potentially treating alcoholic fatty liver disease^[77]. Treatment of type 2 diabetic KKAY mice with perilla oil could promote the enrichment of *Akkermansia* and *Alloprevotella*, while decreasing *Aerococcus* and *Streptococcus*. Thus, perilla oil is a potential functional food to alleviate type 2 diabetes by accelerating the recovery of gut microbiota diversity and mitigating insulin resistance via PI3K/AKT signaling^[78]. Intervention with perilla oil also increases the abundance of SCFA-producing bacteria, such as *Butyrivibrio*, to alleviate the metabolic disorders, regulate intestinal inflammation and permeability, and improve intestinal lipid metabolism and cholesterol metabolism caused by HFD^[79]. Besides, the different doses of perilla oil may exert different effects on gut microbiota. It has shown that low doses of perilla oil obviously increased the abundance of *Alistipes*, *Alloprevotella*, *Parabacteroides* and *Rikenella*, while decreasing the levels of *Desulfovibrio*, *Oscillibacter*, *Blautia*, *unidentified Ruminococcaceae*, *Lachnospiraceae*, *unidentified Lachnospiraceae*, *Angelakisella* and *Bilophila*; the medium and high doses of perilla oil markedly decreased the abundance of *Blautia* in Diabetic KKAY Mice^[46].

Similarly, there is also a relatively small lack of research on the metabolism of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt by gut microbiota, which limits the further understanding of the relationship between gut microbiota and *Perilla frutescens*. Future studies should reveal the dynamic process of the medicine metabolism after it enters the body, thus promoting a better monitoring of its efficacy.

5. Adverse effect of Labiatae TCM

Although Labiatae TCMs possess several pharmacological effects, and its toxic and side effects are smaller than those of chemical or biological drugs, some adverse effects, such as gastrointestinal disorder and liver and kidney injury^[80] cannot be ignored. TCM usually has an appropriate dose range, in which there are usually no toxic and side effects. One clinical research showed that administration of 200, 400, and 600 mg of baicalin tablet were safe in healthy Chinese individuals without severe adverse effects^[81]. Intravenous administration of danshen injection, the aqueous extract of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge, did not lead to death and adverse effects in rats, but the injection site presented

focal inflammation in a dose-dependent manner^[82]. Perillyl alcohol, a compound of *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt, have no toxicity but its active metabolites, perillaldehyde and perillidic acid, were showed higher toxicity both in vitro and in vivo^[83]. However, the above research only involves the extracts or active components of Labiatae TCMs. The adverse effects of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge and *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt are still lacking, and how the gut microbiota participates in the regulation of their adverse effects remains to be further studied.

In general, the therapeutic and side effects of TCM usually exist at the same time. If the dose of the TCM is properly controlled, the herbal medicine usually plays a therapeutic role. Nevertheless, the individual differences may appear in some individuals due to their poor tolerance, and they are prone to gastrointestinal discomfort, which can be alleviated by stopping the drug. Several studies revealed that gut microbiota not only participates in the efficacy of herbal medicines, but also affect the adverse effects of herbal medicines^[84]. For example, gut microbiota can hydrolyze the glycosidic linkage of amygdalin and thus release mandelonitrile, which spontaneously breaks down to generate benzaldehyde and toxic prussic acid^[85]. This suggests that gut microbiota can enhance the toxicity of TCM. In contrary, the gut microbiota can also reduce the adverse effect of TCM. For example, gut microbiota can transform aconitum alkaloids via deacylation, and esterification, and removal of methyl hydroxyl, thereby reduced the toxicity of Fuzi^[86]. However, there is a lack of research on the metabolism of active components of *Scutellaria baicalensis* Georgi, *Salvia miltiorrhiza* Bunge and *Perilla frutescens* (L.) Britt. by gut microbiota, as well as the adverse effects of these three TCM mediated by gut microbiota still remained unknown. All of these need to be further studied.

6. Conclusion and prospect

In conclusion, the pharmacological effect of Labiatae TCM, such as anti-inflammation, anti-oxidation, antitumor, improvement of the cardiovascular system and neural functions, partly mediated by the gut microbiota, which reflecting the important value of the gut microbiota in the efficacy of traditional Chinese medicine. However, at present, most studies only focus on the regulatory effects of Labiatae plants on gut microbiota. These mono-lateral studies usually ignore the interaction between gut microbiota and TCM, which leads to a lack of study on in-depth causal and mechanism research. The future study should promote the exploration of the interaction between gut microbiota and TCM and correlation between gut microbiota and individual responses to drugs. It is necessary to ascertain whether the individual different response to medicine is caused by the distinctive drug metabolism or the accumulation of the drug in the body and lead to its different regulatory effects on the microbiota.

Furthermore, the causal research on the efficacy of TCM and the regulation of gut microbiota are currently deficient. The separation and purification technology of TCM, the study methods of gut microbiota, and the combination of network pharmacology technology and bioinformatics means need to be improved, then preformed causal or mechanism study on gut microbiota and TCM so as to provide strategies for the development of TCM-derived probiotic.

Abbreviations

CAT, catalase; GSH, glutathione; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein-cholesterol; HFD, high-fat-diet; IFN- γ , interferon γ ; IL-6, interleukin 6; iNOS, nitric oxide synthase; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein-cholesterol; MAPK, mitogen-activated protein kinase; MDA, malondialdehyde; ROS, reactive oxygen species; SCFAs, short-chain fatty acids; SOD, superoxide dismutase; TCM, traditional Chinese medicine; TGF- β , transforming growth factor-beta.

Conflicts of interest

All authors declared that there are no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

YNY: Wrote the manuscript and reviewed the manuscript. FZ and JQY: Assisted in manuscript revision. CMW: Conceived and supervised the study and was involved in manuscript revision.

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